

PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS OF TILAWATI BANTEN REGIONAL 2: EFFORTS TO IMPROVE PEOPLE'S QUR'AN LITERACY

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Abstract

This study aims to analyze the performance of the Tilawati Banten Regional 2 organization as a branch institution of Tilawati in Banten that organizes and controls the implementation of Qur'an learning Tilawati Method. The formulation of the research problem is to identify problems in the Tilawati Banten Regional 2 organization, design interventions on problems, implement interventions, evaluate interventions, improve the resulting Qur'anic literacy. This research with Mixed Methods Research is a research design based on philosophical assumptions of inquiry methods that focus on data collection and analysis and combine quantitative data and qualitative data to find better, more comprehensive, valid, reliable and objective research results. The results showed that the basic problems related to performance in Tilawati Banten are still lack of human resources (HR), lack of assistance and coaching to Qur'an instructors and teachers, distance between institutions that are far apart and supervision activities that have not been running. The interventions carried out are improving management, designing Qur'anic learning strategies, conducting training on an ongoing basis, intensive coaching activities for teachers in remote areas, and planning scheduled evaluation and supervision activities in user institutions, improving financial management and others. Evaluation of interventions based on questionnaire analysis of performance variables with a score of 4.20-4.60 classified into the category of very good average score. Tilawati Banten intervenes well according to SOP standards and refers to the vision and mission as well as the organization's work program. Thus, the performance (X) of Tilawati Banten provides a significant correlation with Qur'anic Literacy (Y) at a score of 0.633, meaning that both are positively correlated and quite strong.

Keywords: Analysis. Development, Tilawati, Performance.

INTRODUCTION

Learning the Qur'an with the tilawati method is an innovation in learning the Qur'an in Indonesia (Umar Jaeni et al., 2020). The Tilawati method was born from the anxiety of Qur'an educators at Pesantren Nurul Falah Surabaya about the low ability of the community to read the Qur'an properly and tartil. After implementing this method, Qur'an learning showed improvement (Ardiansah, 2018). The success of the Tilawati method applied by Qur'an educators in Surabaya was then spread throughout Indonesia including in Banten. Several studies in Banten found that there are still many people who have not been able to read the Qur'an properly according to *makhraj* and *tajwid*, even their abilities are categorized as illiterate of the Qur'an (Itang, n.d.,2000). Based on a survey conducted in 2017 of 1,505 respondents by the Banten Tilawatil Qur'an Development Institute (LPTQ) spread across 155 village villages in 50 sub-districts in eight regencies and cities throughout Banten that 12.4 percent or around 1,240,000 people out of 10 million Banten residents could not read the Qur'an, even 12 percent of them could not read the Qur'an at all or were illiterate of the Qur'an. The level of ability to read the Qur'an is also grouped, ranging from very poor to very fluent. The result was that the reading ability in *the high category* was *only 23.28 percent*, the medium category was *50.05 percent*, and the low category was *26.67 percent* (Azizah et al., 2023).

Similarly, data from the results of research by the University of Qur'an Science (PTIQ) suggests that 65 percent of Indonesian people are still illiterate of the Qur'an, mostly in rural areas or remote areas (Riyani, 2021). A national survey conducted by the Qur'an Research and Development Institute of the Ministry of Religious Affairs on 3.7 million out of 7 million students throughout Indonesia stated that the ability to read the Qur'an of high school students / equivalent, fell into the *medium category of 2.59* out of a scale of 5 (Banten, n.d.,2000:25). The latest data related to the ability to read the Qur'an in the General Higher Education (PTU) student environment held at Untirta in 2020, based on the results of the Qur'an reading test conducted on 2,777 first-semester students showed that 40% of the students who were tested for recitation, their ability was categorized as fluent in reading the Qur' an but not in accordance with tajweed. Of course, this situation is very concerning, considering Banten is an area with strong Islamic characteristics. Efforts to update and innovate the Qur'anic learning method were adjusted to the guidance of the times (Pujiana et al., 2020). Learning the Qur'an which is carried out with limited media makes it difficult for students or learners of the Qur'an to achieve the target and ability to master the Qur'an (Mudzakkir, 2013). The birth of the tilawati method with the principle of "learning the Qur'an becomes easy and fun" is expected to accelerate the improvement of the quality of Qur'an learning even better (Afina, 2019).

Allah says in verse 32 of QS Al Qamar which means: "And indeed, We have facilitated the Qur'an for warning, so is there anyone who will take a lesson?". It is this verse that motivates and guarantees that Qur'an learners will find no difficulty in learning it and everyone can easily learn the Qur'an. Based on this motivation, Tilawati Banten was established in 2013 at the Sabilul Qur'an Foundation in Banten. This foundation was established as a connection to the trust of Qur'an fighters in Surabaya to help Tilawati Banten improve Qur'an learning in Banten. Tilawati Banten Regional 2 implements all policies related to Qur'an learning carried out based on central instructions (Irlina, 2019). The study of the Qur'an must be created into a learning that is in demand, not monotonous and not boring (Hermawan et al., 2021). In this case, the birth of the tilawati method as an advancement and a form of innovation from the existing Qur'an learning method. Qur'anic literacy or the ability of Qur'anic literacy that is manifested in the ability to understand, evaluate, and use written texts as a medium of communication in society and develop knowledge must be created by facilitating appropriate methods (Muti'ah, 2020)(Rosdiane Rusdiyanto et al., 2023)

This research is also related to efforts to increase productivity and efficiency of work results in a process of increasing competence by humans and organizations based on the development of systemic and systematic systems as discussed in performance technology (HPT) (Bernardez, 2007) (Hendriyani et al., 2023). Performance Analysis at Tilawati Banten Regional 2 is in line with the discussion of Human Performance Technology based on analysis from the International Society for Performance Improvement (ISPI) which formulates performance as something that concerns activities and measurable outcomes, namely measurable activities and results (more focused on achieving outputs or results) (Sumarno & Setiadi, 2023) (Cho et al., 2011). In its application, the HPT technique from ISPI sees how the performance of Tilawati Banten Regional 2 seeks to carry out its functions and positions as a training institution with a variety of teacher development and focus on the expected results (Fox & Klein, 2008) (Nufus et al., 2023). As a training institution, Tilawati Banten Regional 2 focuses on creating teacher cadres who have qualifications and

competencies in the field of the Tilawati Method, with various training materials in accordance with the purpose of the training (Fitriansyah, 2018) (Mukhlison Effendi, 2021) Research on the success of learning the Qur'an with the Tilawati Method has been carried out a lot, including:

Culture Learning Management Al-Qur'an Model Tilawati to Improve Student Character by Umar Zaeni, research to determine the learning culture, management functions, and learning process of the Qur'an with the Tilawati Method. Knowing character development by learning the Qur'an Tilawati Method at SMP Al Muslim Sidoarjo, SMPN 1 Surabaya and SMPN 34 Surabaya.

This research is a multi-case study with purposive sampling techniques with research subjects in 3 schools. Data collection was carried out by providing questions related to culture, learning management, and learning processes in the three schools. The results of the study concluded that 1) the culture of learning the Qur'an with the Tilawati Method contributes quite well in the formation of student character, 2) the use of management science principles in the implementation of learning the Qur'an Tilawati Method is very appropriate, 3) the learning process of the Qur'an model consists of interrelated components, including graduation targets on quality and quantity, curriculum, management of Qur'an learning with methods Tilawati, 4) to nurture 25 student characters through learning the Qur'an The Tilawati method is carried out by designing learning with syntax or learning stages that are arranged systematically. The implications of this research can be used as material to improve the implementation of the Qur'anic learning culture by developing modern learning management principles (Umar Jaeni et al., 2020). Optimizing the Right Brain in Memorizing Al-Qur'an Juz 30 through the Tilawati Method in Elementary Schools by Zulfatun Anisah. His research concluded that memorization of the Qur'an juz 30 needs to be supported by the suitability of right-brain functionality along with the use of appropriate and appropriate methods. So far in Bangilan sub-district and other nearby sub-districts there is only one school that has a juz 30 memorization program. In addition, reducing children's dependence on gadgets can be busy with activities that are in accordance with their psychological and physical development, namely in the form of children's daily schedules filled with activities that are beneficial to themselves.

This study uses qualitative descriptive methods by obtaining data sources in the form of primary data from interviews, observations, as well as documentation conducted by researchers at SD Islam Cendekia Assalam, and secondary data from literature materials in schools including school vision-mission, teacher data, student data and learning methods applied in schools. The results showed that 9 out of 39 students had been able to memorize juz 30 faster. In just one year, so that starting in grade 2, 9 such students can continue memorization from juz 1. As for the other 30 students, they continued to memorize until they finished juz 30. SD Islam Cendekia Assalam Bangilan chose to use the tilawati method in optimizing right brain function. Long-term memory through music and art can help students more quickly remember and recite verses in surah juz 30 (Anisah, 2020). Introduction to Hijaiyah Letters through Tilawati Method to Students Aged 5-6 by Hunainah, his research to describe the introduction of Hijaiyah letters through the tilawati method; Supporting and inhibiting factors in the recognition of Hijaiyah letters through the Tilawati method for students aged 5-6 years at Al-Qadr Qur'an House, Serang city. Research approach with descriptive qualitative. Data collection techniques use observation, interviews,

documentation, and triangulation. Data is analyzed through reduction, data presentation, and verification. The results of the study stated that (1) the recognition of hijaiyah letters in the Qur'an Al-Qadr House was in accordance with the learning steps contained in the Tilawati Method or learning guide using the following techniques: teacher reading-student listening; teacher reading-student imitation; teachers and students alike read; and individually read and listen using the book tilawati; (2) The contributing factor is that all teachers pray tilawati; complete media; a conducive learning environment; high morale of students and teachers; appropriate curriculum; build teacher and parent communication. As for the inhibiting factor, there are still some parents who don't care; some students rarely attend Qur'anic study classes or arrive late; the student is too tired from activities outside; teacher change in the middle of the semester; inadequate vehicle parking space (Hunainah, Imroatun, Riswanto, 2021). Based on the research above, it is concluded that the method in learning is something very important. The success of a learning is largely determined by choosing the right method. No matter how good the material is, it will not be delivered if it is wrong in choosing the method (Ahmad & Alam, n.d.). With the Tilawati Method developed by Tilawati Banten, it is expected to increase the success of Qur'an learning held in basic education institutions, PAUD, adult level, pesantren, to university level in the Banten region. Like most organizations or institutions, Tilawati Banten in carrying out its performance will certainly encounter obstacles and various limitations. But no matter what the circumstances, always strive so that the goals of the organization can be achieved. Based on the analysis of *Human Performance Technology* from ISPI with the following grand theory:

Figure 1: Human Performance Technology Analysis

The performance of Tilawati Banten as a development organization for the Tilawati Method has an influence on improving the literacy ability of the Banten people. Performance analysis at Tilawati Banten Regional 2 and user institutions as an organization is an analysis of the components of organizational culture, policies, missions, objectives, operating strategies. Process analysis is an analysis of workflow components, job design, inputs, outputs, performance management procedures. And individual analysis is analysis on the components of individual performance objectives, knowledge, skills, work environment, availability of support tools, training, and feedback (Ihsan et al., 2023).(Rosmilawati, 2023)

RESEARCH METHODS

This research with *Mixed Methods Research* is a research design based on philosophical assumptions as well as inquiry methods. *Mixed Methods Research* is also referred to as a methodology that provides philosophical assumptions in showing direction or giving instructions on how to collect data and analyze data as well as a combination of quantitative and qualitative approaches through several phases of the research process (Dixon-Woods, 2010). Researchers collected data by visiting locations in Tilawati Pusat Surabaya in Surabaya, Tilawati Banten Regional 2 located in Safira Regency Serang, and 55 user institutions in Banten. Then the researcher collects and analyzes qualitative data based on the results of the first stage to be combined and interpreted. The general purpose of this design is that quantitative data helps clarify and form initialized qualitative results. The location of the research was carried out in several places, namely Pesantren Al-Qur'an Nurul Falah Surabaya which is located at Jl. Ketintang Timur PTT VB Surabaya Indonesia as a pesantren that creates the tilawati method, then at Tilawati Banten Regional 2 which is located at Permata Safira Housing Block E4/11 Sepang Taktakan Serang City Banten as the main research object that develops the tilawati method in the Banten region and in 55 institutions that use Tilawati Serang City. Based on *VosViewer analysis*, it can be assumed that research on the performance analysis of Tilawati Banten makes this research idea more renewable (Wilson, 2013). Here's what the figure looks like:

Figure 4: VosViewer Analysis

From the display of the picture above, it can be explained that research on the Tilawati method has been carried out, but on different research objects and cases. The last study conducted in 2021 looks at the bright colors shown in the images. It can be said that *State Of the Art* (SOTA) research on *Analysis and Development of Tilawati Banten Regional 2 Performance in Improving Qur'an Literacy in the treasures of science and research* has never been studied before. *Research Novelty* (RN) can be ascertained and guaranteed that this research has never been studied before, so that the novelty of this research or research findings will be something original without plagiarism. The originality of *this research / originality* of research will later contribute or contribute to the building of science. In the next opportunity other researchers will refer to this research, especially cited as a reference source in the sub-chapter "previous research".

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Problems of Tilawati Banten Regional Organization 2

The problem in Tilawati Banten is based on the results of an interview with the Head of Tilawati Banten, namely the lack of human resources (SDM) as an instructor and teacher of Tilawati, both in Tilawati Banten itself and in institutions that use Tilawati. With SDM which is limited, Tilawati Banten continues to provide assistance and coaching to instructors at Tilawati and teachers at user institutions. Assistance and coaching are carried out to improve the ability of instructors and teachers and maintain the quality of learning the Tilawati Method. However, still in carrying out mentoring and coaching are also constrained, with the distance of institutions that are far apart and supervision activities that are not running. User institutions sometimes complain of a lack of assistance while various problems related to technical learning in the field occur a lot and require immediate treatment. User institutions consider it the same to join Tilawati Banten or not. This is what then makes user institutions lose trust and return to using old learning methods.

Another problem is that the learning strategy or tilawati learning strategy has not been fully implemented. Some user institutions, such as Al-Azhar Elementary School, have not fully implemented the tahfidz method as the central standard and still use their own standards. Or the problem of limited human resources such as the case at TPQ Babul Hidayah, which still unites students with different levels in one class, as a result of which children's abilities are not considered properly, which affects the increase in level and so on and many more cases of the inability of institutions to carry out learning procedures from the center. Despite all the limitations, the application of the tilawati method in learning the Qur'an shows good results, it can be seen that there is an increase in the ability felt by user institutions after applying this method (Achyandia, 2016) (Ali & Erihadiana, 2021)(Johan et al., 2020)

The learning process is carried out based on the guidance of the Central Tilawati and is carried out according to standard learning techniques so that the learning process is based on SOPs and uniformly applied in all institutions. The obstacle is that user institutions have not been able to fully carry out learning based on central standards, but are adjusted to the circumstances of their respective institutions. The lack of support from the environment in the form of information and feedback data, and the absence of a behavioral treasury in the form of motivation and appreciation from

Tilawati Banten are feared to cause the performance of user institutions and branch tilawati to decline.

2. Intervention in Banten Tilawati Organization 2

Based on the identification of the above problems, Tilawati Banten made various efforts to solve these problems, namely by: a). Increasing staff and administrative personnel, so that data related to institutions can be absorbed for improvement, in addition to administrative order, b). Special infrastructure. namely in order to provide satisfaction with the service of students and students of Tilawati and the implementation of training, the provision of its own building is prioritized, c). Long-term strategic planning, which is prepared in a planned manner, d). The learning process, which is supported by various infrastructure, is effective as much as possible, e). Performance support, f). Analysis of work, g). Work design, h). Personal development, i). Human resource development through training and other human resource improvement, j). Good organizational communication, k). Design and development of the organization, l). The financial system is more transparent and accountable. In relation to overcoming the lack of human resources, the effort made is to organize training programmatically for Qur'an teachers of the tilawati method. The following trainings have been carried out in Tilawati Banten, namely:

Table 5: Training of Tilawati Institute

NO	NAMA DIKLAT	JUMLAH PES	BERSYAHADAH	BELUM BERSY	
1	STANDARISASI GURU AL-QURAN LEVEL 1	13 GURU	12	1	
2	STANDARISASI GURU AL-QURAN LEVEL 1	50 GURU	19	31	
3	STANDARISASI GURU AL-QURAN LEVEL 1	34 GURU	18	16	
4	STANDARISASI GURU AL-QURAN LEVEL 1	44 GURU	5	39	
5	STANDARISASI GURU AL-QURAN LEVEL 1	41 GURU	12	29	
6	STANDARISASI GURU AL-QURAN LEVEL 1	68 GURU	10	58	
7	STANDARISASI GURU AL-QURAN LEVEL 1	89 GURU	11	78	
8	STANDARISASI GURU AL-QURAN LEVEL 1	69 GURU	18	51	
9	STANDARISASI GURU AL-QURAN LEVEL 1	48 GURU	16	32	
10	STANDARISASI GURU AL-QURAN LEVEL 1	83 GURU	15	68	
11	STANDARISASI GURU AL-QURAN LEVEL 2	36 GURU	35	1	
12	STANDARISASI GURU AL-QURAN LEVEL 1	50 GURU	25	25	
13	STANDARISASI GURU AL-QURAN LEVEL 2	27 GURU	26	1	
14	MUNAQOSYAH SANTRI	10 SANTRI	10	0	
15	MUNAQOSYAH SANTRI	12 SANTRI	9	3	
16	STANDARISASI GURU AL-QURAN LEVEL 1	47 GURU	7	40	
17	STANDARISASI GURU AL-QURAN LEVEL 1	59 GURU	9	50	
18	STANDARISASI GURU AL-QURAN LEVEL 1	29 GURU	27	2	
19	STANDARISASI GURU AL-QURAN LEVEL 1	48 GURU	9	39	
20	TRAINING OF TRAINER	64 GURU			
21	STANDARISASI GURU AL-QURAN LEVEL 1	32 GURU	6	26	
22	STANDARISASI GURU AL-QURAN LEVEL 1	29 GURU	6	23	
23	STANDARISASI GURU AL-QURAN LEVEL 1	29 GURU	14	15	

However, the trainings held by Tilawati Banten are still limited to Qur'an standardization training level 1 and level 2 only, once ToT training and two Munaqosyah Santri trainings. Of course, this intervention has not been effective in improving the performance of Tilawati Banten, so the implementation of training must be further evaluated.

3. Implementation of Intervention in Regional Banten Tilawati Organization

a. Change management.

Tilawati Banten conducts a clear division of tasks according to fields, so that work is more efficient. The distribution of tasks is carried out so that everything runs regularly and is completed on time, always growing discipline, through the provision of certain punishments or rewards. Command is based on a single source so that direction and purpose are common, and in the common interest. Prioritizing public interests over personal interests by providing fair and equitable rewards, as well as position levels to clarify their respective duties. Order and all things are in the right position. Leaders are fair to all employees without discriminating in carrying out their duties, initiative to do their respective jobs or duties in order to uphold the vision and mission of the organization (Abaci & Pershing, 2017).(Taswirul Afkar, 2007).

b. Qur'an learning strategies that have been prepared are adjusted to the level or level of education of students.

c. Consultation process.

In the consultation process, Tilawati Banten provides many opportunities for user institutions to open 24-hour online services so that the problems of their respective institutions can be resolved as soon as possible. This is the function of Tilawati Branch as an extension of Tilawati Pusat which is mandated to provide solutions in their respective regions.

d. Employee and staff development.

Tilawati branch has employees or staff and instructors who are competent in their fields and facilitates Tilawati Branch to develop the Tilawati method to remote areas in Banten, especially Serang City. Tilawati Banten improves her performance with instructors as follows:

Table 6: Tilawati Banten 2 Instructor Data

No	Name Trainer	Learning Strategy Instructor	Song Instructor
1	AHMAD MA'MUN, AL HAFIZH	V	V
2	ALTAF SYAUQI IQBAL SAIFANI, M. Pd.	V	V
3	CHOIRUL MARZUKI, S. Pd	V	V
4	DEDE IMTIHANUDIN, M. Pd.I	V	V
5	EMA NURMAWATI	V	V
6	ENENG YUYUN YUNIARSIH, S. Pd.I	V	V
7	JUMANTA, M. Pd.I	V	V
8	MADHATA, S. Sy, AL HAFIZH	V	V
9	MUHAMMAD FAUZI, S. Kom	V	V
10	RIAN NUGRAHA, S. Pd.I	V	V
11	SAIFULLAH, M. Pd.I	V	V
12	SITI MAEMUNAH, S. Ud	V	V
13	SUKAWATI	V	
14	TITIN ROHILAH, S.E	V	V
15	TO'ATILLAH, S.H	V	V
16	YAYAN HARIYANTO, S.Ud	V	V
17	RIFA MA'ARIFAH, S. q, aL HAFIZHOH	V	

e. Communication Patterns.

Communication success is the most important part of realizing improved performance of educational organizations. Without communication, the organization does not function in carrying out its original goals (Bariqi, 2020). It is necessary to build healthy and conducive communication so that positive reactions arise. Techniques in creating an effective organizational atmosphere can encourage interaction and communication so that educational goals will be achieved optimally. Communication cannot be denied as a development strategy for improving the performance of educational organizations. In Tilawati Banten, the form of communication is applied in active consultation between branches and user institutions to improve performance both for their own branches and user institutions.

f. Social Relations and Building Unions.

In establishing social relations too, that among user institutions with various existing Qur'anic learning methods, social relations are guaranteed and these user institutions bind their institutions in different organizations, both BKPRMI, BKPAKSI and IGRA and others. The union was established to accommodate user institutions in relation to their formal interests and shared educational vision.

3. Evaluation of Intervention in Tilawati Banten Regional Organization 2.

In carrying out interventions, an evaluation is carried out to see the success or failure of a process. The following are the results of descriptive analysis of efforts or interventions carried out by Tilawati Branch, namely:

Table 7: Performance Analysis of Tilawati Banten

CODE	STATEMENT	SS	S	RR	KS	TS	AVERAGE
Q1	The vision of Tilawati Banten is based on Qur'anic literacy	33	22	0	0	0	4,60
Q2	The mission of Tilawati Banten is based on the development of tilawati in improving Qur'an literacy	31	23	0	1	0	4,53
Q3	So far, Tilawati Banten has a tilawati team that focuses on improving Qur'an literacy	25	28	1	1	0	4,40
Q4	So far, Tilawati Banten has communicated/partnered with institutions using tilawati	21	30	4	0	0	4,31
Q5	So far, Tilawati Banten has been responsive in responding to institutional requests	23	29	3	0	0	4,36
Q6	So far, Tilawati Banten has social media facilities to facilitate interaction with tilawati user institutions	23	31	1	0	0	4,40
Q7	So far, Tilawati Banten has SOPs in the operation of the Tilawati Banten work program	24	29	2	0	0	4,40
Q8	So far, the Banten Tilawati Team has carried out its duties according to the established SOP	26	26	3	0	0	4,42

Q9	So far, the implementation of the Banten Tilawati Training is in accordance with the work program	20	33	2	0	0	4,33
Q10	So far, the Banten Tilawati training program has been carried out continuously between the training before and after.	18	35	2	0	0	4,29
Q11	So far, the Tilawati Banten training program has been carried out periodically according to the work program.	19	33	2	1	0	4,27
Q12	So far, Tilawati Banten has a program to upgrade tilawati instructors and teachers regularly	19	34	2	0	0	4,31
Q13	So far, Tilawati Banten Branch has its own building.	19	32	4	0	0	4,27
Q14	So far, Tilawati Banten has the appropriate facilities and infrastructure.	16	35	4	0	0	4,22
Q15	So far, Tilawati Banten has the appropriate learning media.	24	30	1	0	0	4,42
Q16	So far, Tilawati Banten has guaranteed the quality of learning the Qur'an	21	30	4	0	0	4,31
Q17	So far, Tilawati Banten has been running the organization according to SOP	18	33	4	0	0	4,25
Q18	So far, Tilawati Banten has been actively collaborating with other parties in order to improve the development of Banten tilawati performance	19	35	1	0	0	4,33
Q19	During this time Tilawati Banten has been actively cooperating in order to improve the literacy of the Qur'an.	19	33	3	0	0	4,29
Q20	Supervision of Tilawati Banten is carried out according to SOP	21	32	2	0	0	4,35
Q21	Tilawati Banten has a supervisory team that works independently	15	36	4	0	0	4,20
Q22	The supervisory team at Tilawati Banten carries out its duties periodically	16	34	5	0	0	4,20
Q23	Supervision of Tilawati Banten using validated instruments	18	33	4	0	0	4,25
Q24	One of the goals of Tilawati Banten is that with the Tilawati method students are able to read the Qur'an fluently and tartil.	27	28	0	0	0	4,49
Q25	The ability to read the Qur'an fluently and tartil is done on a regular schedule.	25	28	2	0	0	4,42
Q26	There is a clear guide in teaching the Qur'an to read the Qur'an eloquently and tartil.	27	28	0	0	0	4,49
AVERAGE	4,35						

Based on the table above, in the performance variable statement item, the average score was obtained ranging from 4.20 to 4.60. The lowest average score was found in Q21 and Q22 statement items with an average score of 4.20. Meanwhile, the highest average score was found in the Q1 statement item with an average score of 4.60. In addition, the average score of all statement items was also obtained at 4.35. The average score of 4.35 is classified into the category of very good average score. It can be explained based on descriptive data that the evaluation of interventions in the form of efforts carried out by Tilawati Banten is good. Tilawati Banten has carried out its performance in accordance with SOP standards and refers to the vision and mission as well as the organization's work program. The efforts made by Tilawati Banten have shown itself as an independent institution that stands on Islamic syiar, namely spreading the Qur'an throughout the world.

5. Increasing Qur'an Literacy in Tilawati Banten 2.

The following is the output of increasing literacy in reading the Qur'an of the community based on the performance of Tilawati Banten from 55 respondents, namely:

Table 8: Analysis of Community Qur'anic Literacy Output

CODE	STATEMENT	SS	S	RR	KS	TS	AVERAGE
Q27	Santri is able to read the Qur'an because the teacher has competence.	26	28	1	0	0	4,45
Q28	Santri is able to write the Qur'an correctly and beautifully.	21	32	2	0	0	4,35
Q29	Santri is able to write the Qur'an correctly and beautifully because it is done on a regular schedule	16	36	3	0	0	4,24
Q30	Santri is able to write the Qur'an because there are clear guidelines in teaching to write the Qur'an.	16	36	3	0	0	4,24
Q31	Santri can write the Qur'an well and beautifully because it is taught by teachers who have competence.	17	34	4	0	0	4,24
Q32	Santri is able to translate the Qur'an correctly.	13	38	4	0	0	4,16
Q33	Santri is able to translate the Qur'an correctly because learning is carried out on a regular schedule.	11	41	3	0	0	4,15
Q34	Santri can translate the Qur'an correctly because there is a guide.	14	39	2	0	0	4,22
Q35	Santri is able to translate because it is taught by teachers who have competence in translating the Qur'an.	15	37	3	0	0	4,22
Q36	Santri is able to learn the Qur'an well.	20	34	1	0	0	4,35
Q37	Santri is able to learn the Qur'an well because learning is carried out on a regular schedule.	18	35	2	0	0	4,29
Q38	Santri is able to learn the Qur'an because there are clear guidelines in learning the Qur'an well.	15	38	2	0	0	4,24

Q39	Santri tilawati is able to memorize the Qur'an correctly.	19	34	2	0	0	4,31
Q40	Santri is able to memorize the Qur'an correctly because it is done on a regular schedule.	19	33	3	0	0	4,29
Q41	Santri is able to memorize using a guide.	18	37	0	0	0	4,33
Q42	Students' reading ability improved	13	16	14	10	2	3,51
Q43	students' writing skills improved	10	18	15	12	0	3,47
Q44	The students' memorization ability increases	1	15	21	12	6	2,87
Q45	The ability to learn students increases	1	27	18	4	5	3,27
Q46	The ability to translate students has increased	1	15	14	10	15	2,58
AVERAGE	3,99						

Based on the table above, the Quran Literacy Variable statement item obtained an average score ranging from 2.58 to 4.45. The lowest average score was found in the Q46 statement item with an average score of 2.58. Meanwhile, the highest average score was found in the Q27 statement item with an average score of 4.45.

Besides, it also obtained an average score of all statement items of 3.99. The average score of 3.99 is classified into the category of good average score. This means that the performance carried out by Tilawati Banten with good output is based on questionnaires submitted to 55 institutions as respondents.

CONCLUSION

Research on Performance Analysis of Tilawati Banten Regional 2 with Human Performance Technology (*HPT*) analysis, namely examining fundamental problems related to performance in Tilawati Banten, determining intervention design based on ISPI (International Society for Performance Improvement) model analysis which formulates performance as something that concerns activities and measurable outcomes i.e. measurable activities and results focused on achieving outputs or results. Implementing interventions carried out by organizing various trainings, evaluating interventions based on performance variable questionnaire analysis and conducting correlation analysis between Banten Tilawati Performance and Qur'an Literacy and it is stated that high Banten Tilawati Performance is followed by high or increased Qur'an literacy.

IMPLICATION

The findings of the study showed that the performance of Tilawati Banten had a good impact on increasing Qur'an literacy. Problems in Tilawati Banten must be immediately found solutions so that they are immediately followed up, and the success of Tilawati Banten must be accompanied by consistency in the development of the Tilawati Method in user institutions, namely Al-Qu'an learning institutions in Banten through programmed supervision.

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